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Annotation This article analyzes the history of the formation, stages of development and current state of teaching methods in fine arts. Based on historical sources and modern research, information is provided about pedagogical approaches to art education, the impact of innovative technologies on the educational process, and methods used in teaching art.

Keywords: fine arts, teaching methods, pedagogy, innovative technologies, art education, creative approach.

Introduction Fine arts are an important part of human thought and culture, and their role in the educational process is incomparable. The history of teaching methodology dates back to ancient centuries, and various pedagogical approaches have been formed in this process. This article analyzes the history of the formation, development and current state of the methodology of teaching fine arts. Although the initial information on the teaching of fine arts in the world is not enough, there are materials from ancient Egypt and Greece dating back to the 3rd century BC. In ancient Egypt, sculptures carved into mountain rocks, as well as paintings, continue to amaze people with their high artistry and technique of work. It should be noted that, regardless of the form in which such works of art are, they cannot be created without special schools. It is no exaggeration to say that people have been passing on their experiences to subsequent generations in various ways since the time of primitive communities. This is evidenced by historical sources about the teaching of drawing in ancient Egypt.

Figure 1. Statues carved into mountain rocks in ancient Egypt

The fact that people have been engaged in teaching fine arts since ancient times is preserved in many ancient Egyptian sources. In Egyptian schools, teaching drawing was systematically carried out in conjunction with drawing. According to historical information, young people graduating from school were required to be able to measure the surface of a certain area and record it on paper, draw a building plan, and describe the scheme of ditches and canals. Drawing was also of great importance in teaching

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

children to write. For example, a drawing of a foot was drawn to teach the letter “o”, and a drawing of a hand was drawn to teach the letter “q”. When teaching children to draw, special attention was paid to the free movement of the hand. Free, light, smooth lines were drawn on a blackboard or papyrus. It should also be noted that since only children studied in schools of this period, high demands were placed on them. Therefore, if the requirements and instructions were not followed, children were severely punished, even beaten with sticks.

Although it is not known whether there was a theory of teaching drawing in Egyptian schools, some drawing rules were used. Teachers taught drawing (shape, color, size, structure, etc.) not based on observation of nature, but by copying from a large sample, a scheme.

According to some information, teaching drawing in Egypt began much earlier than in ancient Greece. The 15th-century Italian architect, artist, writer and scientist L.B. Alberti writes: “According to the Egyptians, painting existed among them six thousand years before the Greeks.”

Teaching to paint was also carried out in ancient Greece in its own way. In teaching painting, special attention was paid to the study of nature, all of creation, and the perception of beauty in it. To paint, beeswax was applied to a wooden board and painted over with paint. The drawing was drawn on this surface with a sharp metal or bone. An incorrectly drawn drawing was rubbed by hand, filling in the lines and erasing them. Then a new drawing was made on a flat surface.

In 432 BC, the Greek sculptor Polykleitos created the Statue of Doriphorus as an example of the proportion and proportionality between the parts of the human body. Later, it was taught in all special artistic and non-artistic schools. Greek artists developed laws and rules for depicting life and beauty based on observation. In their opinion, beauty is expressed in the most beautiful, orderly, rhythmic and symmetrical, proportionality between parts, and correct mathematical relationships. Later, several specific schools of painting emerged in Greece. Among them, the Sicyon school played a major role in the development of fine arts and its teaching. The teaching work in this school was organized on a scientific basis, and the children were focused on the vastness of nature, on the knowledge of its laws. Among the graduates of this school were such famous artists as Pamphilus. Pamphilus showed the educational and educational value of drawing. His contemporary Pliny wrote about this: “Through his efforts, first in Sicyon, and then in Greece, the necessity of teaching drawing to all children was established. It was noted that primary education began with drawing.” During the Renaissance, Italian fine arts and the method of teaching it played a large role. During this period, drawing was included in the list of subjects of general education. Famous artists such as Cennino Cennini, Leon Battista Alberti, and Leonardo da Vinci did remarkable work in this regard. In their works, the relationship between science and art, issues of proportion, perspective, and anatomy played a key role. According to their views, drawing from nature should be the basis of education.

Leonardo da Vinci, in particular, had a great influence on the development of the methodology of teaching fine arts. In his work "Book of Painting", he considered painting as a serious scientific discipline. For many years, he developed the laws of anatomy, color, and proportion between human organs. A. Dürer, a German artist of the Renaissance, made a great contribution to the improvement of teaching fine arts. He was the first to invent a geometric method to facilitate drawing. In his opinion, geometric shapes are the basis of any object, part, and surface. Therefore, when drawing, when depicting certain objects, geometric shapes must first be drawn, and then they are generalized to create a real image. Later, his method began to be widely used in the pedagogical activities of Dupuy, Ashbe, Chistyakov, etc. Even today, this method has not lost its power.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

The great merit of the artists of the Renaissance was that they substantiated the enormous importance of anatomy, perspective, and light and shadow in fine art. As a result, works of art began to amaze the audience with their high artistry and realism. Despite this, they were not able to create a system of teaching fine arts. These problems began to be solved mainly from the 16th century. The work was facilitated by the establishment of a number of academies. Such academies were opened in cities such as Florence, Rome, and Bologna. Previously, such schools were founded by private individuals, but now the state and communities also contributed to this. Among these educational institutions, the Art Academy, opened by the famous painters, sculptors and teachers, the Carrara brothers and their cousins, Agostino and Annibale, left a great mark. In the educational system they created, the main role was played by the rapid mastery of educational materials, the formation of students' skills in painting based on scientific knowledge, regular practice, laws and rules.

These artist-teachers tried to summarize the experience and achievements of their predecessors and educate students on this basis. In their work, they paid special attention to the issues of light, shade, color, structure, anatomy, and perspective. Judging by some historical and art history information, a number of theoretical and practical manuals were created by Dürer. However, some of them have survived, and are incomplete. According to the academic system, one cannot learn to paint without serious scientific knowledge. Children learn to be creative through drawing. This quality was considered necessary for every person, regardless of the field in which he is a specialist. Later, under the influence of the Academy of Bologna, such academies were opened in Paris, Vienna, Berlin, Madrid, St. Petersburg, and London. The usefulness of teaching fine arts in all general education schools was developed by the great Czech educator J.A. Comenius in his work "Great Didactics".

The methodology of teaching fine arts has been formed since the early stages of human history. In the early periods, art was taught mainly through practical experience, but later special schools were established. For example, in ancient Egypt, Greece and Rome, the tradition of a master-disciple relationship in painting and sculpture was widespread. In the Middle Ages, fine arts were taught for religious purposes in monasteries and religious schools.

With the advent of the Renaissance, art education reached a new level. Great artists such as Leonardo da Vinci and Michelangelo founded their own schools and formed the principles of studying and teaching fine arts on a scientific basis. In the 18th-19th centuries, art academies appeared and they played an important role in art education.

The ideas of the French scientist J.J. Rousseau on the improvement of painting in the general education system are noteworthy. In his book "Emile and Education", he proved the great importance of painting from nature in understanding the world. In his opinion, it is most effective to paint in the midst of nature. Because, children see the true color of things in nature, their perspective reductions with their own eyes, and consciously understand its laws.

Among European teachers, I.V. Goethe (Germany), I.G. Pestalozzi, I. Schmidt and P. Schmidt (Switzerland), A. Dupuy and F. Dupuy (France) made a great contribution to the teaching of drawing as a separate subject in general education schools and its improvement.

Teachers such as N. Pestalozzi, P. Schmidt and I. Schmidt advocated the advantages of geometric methods over natural methods in general education schools. As a result, two opposing trends emerged in the teaching of drawing in schools, based on the natural and geometric methods. While the advantages of drawing based on nature were advocated by Y.A. Comenius, J.J. Rousseau, and I.V. Goethe, the geometric method was mainly promoted by I.G. Pestalozzi, I.Schmidt and P.Schmidt, and F.Dupuis. However, from the second half of the 19th century, the geometric method began to be

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

used in many European countries. Thus, by the middle of the 19th century, the teaching of drawing as a subject in general education schools in Europe was quite developed. In addition to artists and teachers, art historians, educators, psychologists, and doctors began to engage in this field. A number of publications on the methodology of teaching drawing began to be published. Kullman, Prang, Elsner, Baumgart, Ausberg, Braunschwig, Tedd, and others showed great dedication in this regard. Although the literature created by them contained contradictory views on the rules of drawing and its methodology, there were no such contradictory views on the natural method. At the beginning of the 20th century, a biogenetic theory of children's visual creativity emerged. In this regard, the German scientist G. Kerschensteiner, the Russian art critic A. Bakushinsky, and the American J. Dupuis were active. According to their opinion, one should not interfere with the artistic creativity of children. They should create freely. One cannot accelerate education by interfering with their creativity. Because each child passes through stages predetermined in advance according to their age. Without passing this stage, one cannot master the next, or it is impossible to interfere with their creativity and change their thoughts and feelings. Therefore, they wrote that guiding and interfering in the creativity of children is a crime. Later, this idea was called "Free Education".

Drawing appeared as a general education subject in Russian schools at the beginning of the 18th century. During this period, drawing was taught at the Naval Academy, the School of Surgery, the Cadet School, the Gymnasium under the Academy of Sciences, and the Girls' Educational Institution. In these educational institutions, drawing was considered not to prepare artists, but as a necessary subject for young people in their professional activities and future lives. In 1934, the Russian artist A. Sapozhnikov created the first textbook for general education schools called "Drawing Course". This textbook was based on drawing from nature. The textbook was built on the basis of realistic painting, and the laws of perspective and light and shadow were also reflected in it. At the same time, Sapozhnikov created a set of methodological tools for demonstrating the structure of objects, perspective reduction, and size from materials such as wire, cardboard, and plaster. According to the author's recommendations, any natural basis is based on geometric shapes of various volumes and surfaces, and therefore the use of the geometric method in drawing is appropriate for the purpose.

One of the creators of a major fundamental work on the teaching of fine arts in general education schools in Russia was G.A. Gippius. His work "Essays on the Theory of Drawing as a General Educational Subject" reflected the most advanced ideas of that time in teaching drawing. When drawing began to be taught in Russian schools on a mass basis, the problem of a shortage of artist-teachers arose.

In order to train special teachers, in 1825 a new department was opened at the Stroganov Technical Drawing School in Moscow, where drawing teachers began to be trained. Since 1879, a training course for drawing teachers was opened at the St. Petersburg Academy of Arts. The program and methodological materials for these courses were prepared by the professor of the Academy of Arts P. Chistyakov. In the programs and manuals compiled during this period, A. Sapozhnikov's geometric transfer methods were excluded from practice, and it was noted that drawing lessons at school consisted only of drawing based on the natural method. These programs and manuals also stipulated the need to give children freedom in their visual activities. In solving the problems of drawing, the "Society of Drawing Teachers", organized in Moscow and St. Petersburg at the beginning of the 19th century, did significant work. Despite the fact that during this period, the issues of teaching drawing aroused great interest among specialists, opposing ideas in this area also intensified. One of these was the formalist movement. Bakushinsky, one of the representatives of this movement, played a major

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

role in promoting the ideas of Kershensteiner and Dupuy in Russia. In his opinion, there is no need for a “School” in art education, nor is it necessary to teach children, they should do what they want, the teacher should only observe. The manuals “Drawing at the Initial Level of Education in Connection with Glue and Ink” by V.I. Beyer and A.K. Voskresensky, published in St. Petersburg in 1918, contained sections on drawing from nature, illustrative drawing, decorative drawing, and observation of pictures.

The emergence of these opposing trends in art education and upbringing was caused by the 1917 coup d'état in Russia and the establishment of the former Soviet Power. This theory of education and upbringing was later severely criticized by the ruling Bolshevik Party, and art education was directed towards the implementation of the tasks of communist education. On the basis of the state resolution “On Primary and Secondary Schools” of September 5, 1931, the goals and objectives of this subject in school programs were revised. One of the people who had a great influence on the formation of Russian Soviet art education was D.N. Kardovsky. This art education system was based on the principles of realistic art, and in 1942, on the initiative and efforts of D.N. Kardovsky, the Faculty of Art and Graphics was opened at the Moscow Pedagogical Institute.

The “Central Houses of Children's Art Education”, established in 1933, played an important role in improving the methodology of drawing in Russia. In connection with the activities of this center, P.Ya. Pavlinov's “Graphic Grammar”, N. Radlov's “Drawing from Nature”, “Collection of Tasks for Drawing”, Ya. Bashilov and E. Kondakhchan's “Children's Drawing” and other manuals were published.

One of the most effective figures in Russia after the Second World War was E. Kondakhchan. In his manual “Methods of Teaching Drawing in Secondary School”, he wrote that, based on advanced experience in this regard, the basis of teaching realistic art and drawing should be drawing from nature. He opposed Bakushinsky's theory of “Free Education”, which was widely promoted in Russia in 1925-50, and staunchly defended the great leadership activity of the teacher in education and upbringing. He tried to justify his ideas by saying that the theory of “Free Education” was a “method” that reduced the role of the teacher and created chaos in teaching. In the second half of the 20th century, a number of scientific and research works were carried out on teaching methods. As a result, in 1963-70, test textbooks on drawing for grades I-VI were prepared and published.

Today, a combination of traditional and modern methods is observed in fine arts education. As a result of the development of computer technologies and digital art programs, interactive teaching methods are widely used. Special programs have been developed in the areas of painting, design, graphics and digital art.

Also, a differentiated approach to teaching art, taking into account the individuality of students and the use of innovative pedagogical technologies are playing an important role. Modern methods are aimed at developing independent thinking of students and involving them in creative activities.

Conclusion The methodology of teaching fine arts has gone through a long historical development. Currently, it is developing as a complex pedagogical system that includes traditional and modern technologies. In the future, the formation of more effective and innovative approaches in this area is expected. In conclusion, it should be said that the goals and objectives of the subject of drawing and the content of education in Russian schools were revised several times, based on government resolutions on reforming the content of education. As a result, in 1970, the name of the subject “Drawing” was changed to “Fine Arts”. The program prepared under this name expanded the tasks of aesthetic education and sections on the study of the works of artists.

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THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

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